

DAMAGE DETECTION OF STRUCTURES OF CULTURAL RELEVANCE.

APPLYING CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORKS

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INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND

As Engineers and Built Industry professionals, we are tasked with design, constructing and maintaining infrastructure we need to support our life activities. These range from Bridges, School buildings, places of residence and religious places. But due varying factors such as in service life load response fatigue, Wind induced Structural Damage as well as Varying degrees of Seismic damage

The conventional method, involves an inspector with the relevant expertise using a crack gauge or determines the size through a visual evaluation, results in a subjective evaluation of the extent of concrete life. Currently, an operator inspects the concrete structure by visually examining the concrete surface However, this method presents numerous problems, including increased risk when the inspector has to work in extremely dangerously high engineering sites. measurements are the subject of several studies focused on damage assessment (Finotti, Cury, and Barbosa 2019).The manual inspection of concrete structures, such as tall buildings, bridges, and huge infrastructures can be time-consuming and costly, and damage assessment is a crucial task that requires the close-range inspection of all surfaces(Malche, Tharewal, and Dhanaraj 2023)

Why risk a valuable human life when we could deploy technology. We Therefore, sought to used machine learning approached to extract the features of structural infrastructure to detect various structural damage forms. (Mir et al. 2022) Structural Damage can be classified into 3 main classes as illustrated below:

Figure 1- Structural Damage Classification with Examples Chart.

SHM TECHNOLOGY EVOLUTION

The main concern of built industry professionals is our ability to detect damage and immediately performing maintenance and remedying actions to return structural elements to optimum functioning performance levels. In recent Decades technologies applied in the Structural Health Monitoring field have and the diagram below illustrates the evolution of Structural Health Technologies.

Figure 2- Evolution of SHM Technologies

Visual Inspection- This usually entails engineers applying various analytical techniques such as Finite Element Methods to predict most probable local and global damage locations and occasionally inspecting them to detect and remedy damage as and when it occurs. This has its limitation and associated problems. Risk to experts in undertaking inspection and limitations to human sensory Organs and very limited technological application and usage,

Smart Sensor Based Systems- We study the behavior of various materials under various structure in-service usage condition and develop and calibrate such materials to be able to detect damage within such structures. A classical example is the Piezoelectric Sensor Based System (PZT). PZT's are materials that generate electric charge voltage when exposed to pressure. The Voltage generated is measured and monitored and analyzed using various mathematical techniques such as the Fourier Transform to detect damage and abnormal sectional material behaviour. Such technologies can be employed under the minutest of detection scenarios to in detecting over 200 km range pipeline damage.

Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence Systems- We mimic human systems and develop computer models which we can train effectively to detect and classify various structural damages. It is a high effective choice since the computer when supported with appropriate Technology has the ability to overcome various human limitations and has a wide applicability range. The Datasets used in these systems ranges from CSV tabled image data, to Varying Characterized images, to 4th Dimensioned Videos.

Identification through image processing is been applied in various fields, including product examination and more recently infrastructure inspection, such as identifying cracks in structures.

GHANA'S INDEPENDENCE ARCH.

THE CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE

Figure 3- The Independence Arch, Accra-

after furthering his education and decided that it was time the back took control managing his affairs and begun the struggle to our independence. It took numerous unsightly periods of unrest till we The British eventually, seeded off control to Ghanaians. After Osagyefo Dr. Kwame Nkrumah declared the Nation as independent, he was appointed as the nation's First ever Ghanaian Prime minister. In spite of Dr. Nkrumah's phenomenal achievement of leading Ghana (then the Gold Coast) to independence, the emerging nation did not have full control of administering our affairs; the battle was not over. On 1st July, 1960 Dr. Nkrumah declared; "*Ghana, our beloved country is free forever*". This was when we achieved Republic status and Osagyefo Dr. Kwame Nkrumah was declared as our first ever President. This declaration was made at the independence square, approximately 50 meters from the Independence Arch, Osu, Accra-Ghana; the nation's capital. In 1961 during Queen Elizabeth II official visit to Ghana, she commissioned the Arch. The Arch can be broken-down in to 2 main parts

Ghana prior to gaining its independence on 6th March, 1957 was called the Gold Coast and was administratively governed by Her Royal Majesty, the Queen of England. The British named the Colony the gold coast, due its rich mineral deposition wealth which was exploited by our Colonial Master. In 1949, a humble servant of the land, known as Kwame Nkrumah returned home from England

- i. **The Crown**; The 4 directional facing black star
- ii. **The Gateway**: to the new Africa

THE LOCATION AND GEOMETRY

The independence Arch's geographical coordinates are latitude 5°32'55.77"N and longitude 0°11'33.96"W. It is located at the roundabout intersection along the 28th February Road; a road named after military veterans who lost their lives in requesting for their World War II service benefits. This monument is approximately 600 meters from the Gulf of Guinea.

Due to its proximity to the Atlantic Ocean and it's at the mercy of the gruesome, relentless condition of its immediate environment. Concrete Structures exposed to marine environmental conditions have reduced working owing to the severe exposure to the chemical ingress, and continuous contact with the humid air, and saline conditions (Somaiya and Bhogayata 2023). According to Table 3 of the 1st quarter, 2009, Independence Arch Environment's Exposure is defined as extreme (No Title n.d.).

Figure 4- 25 Meter Elevated UAV Image of The Independence Arch

Environment	Exposure Classification
Mild	Concrete surfaces protected against weather or aggressive conditions, except those situated in coastal areas
Moderate	Concrete surface sheltered from severe rain or freezing whilst wet; concrete exposed to condensation and rain concrete continuously under water; concrete in contact or buried under non-aggressive soil/ground water; concrete surfaces sheltered from saturated salt air in coastal area
Severe	Concrete surfaces exposed to severe rain, alternate wetting and drying or occasional freezing whilst wet or severe condensation; concrete completely immersed in sea water; concrete exposed to coastal environment
Very Severe	Concrete surfaces exposed to sea water spray, corrosive fumes or severe freezing conditions whilst wet; concrete in contact with or buried under aggressive sub-soil/ground water
Extreme	Surface of members in tidal zone; members in direct contact with liquid/solid aggressive chemicals

Due to this and Reinforced Concrete inherent porous properties, it is prone to cosmetic structural damages such as Cracking and Spalling.

STRUCTURE DESCRIPTION AND POST COLONIAL SYMBOLISM AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT

The 336m² post-colonial edifice is supported by a simple post and beam Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete core structure, with the 4-directional facing black Star Crown and a dazzling 16-panel waffled ceiling hovering above it.

Figure 5- South-East Direction Image

The Edifice houses Ghana's Independence Cenotaph, which bears the names of the gallant heroes of the land who lost their lives on Ghana's Road to independence. During commissioning of the ceremony, Both Osagyefo Dr. Kwame Nkrumah and Her Royal Majesty Queen Elizabeth walked through Arch to symbolize the beginning of the new Era in Ghana and Africa as a whole.

Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, The Government of Ghana under the Auspices of the Ministry of Tourism launched the Programme themed: The Year of Return – A Government Initiative to connect Afro people in the diaspora with African roots with the Ghanaian Heritage and Ancestry. The Independence Arch one of the main sites, reminding all of the Ghanaian being the hope and inspiration for Africa. In the year of return, Tourism contributed 3.7468 billion usd to Ghana's GDP. The following Graph Highlights Tourism direct contribution to the Ghanaian Economy since 2019

Travel, Tourism & Hospitality

Contribution of travel and tourism to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Ghana from 2019 to 2023

(in million U.S. dollars)

Figure 6-Tourism's Contribution Ghana's GDP from 2019-2023

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM

APPLICATION OF CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR STRUCTURAL CRACK DETECTION

Conventionally, concrete is every infrastructure designer's first choice of material primarily because

- Relatively Cheaper material cost
- Great compressive stress resistance
- Adaptability to various mold shape.
- Ease of availability.

In spite of the above-mentioned strengths, Ordinary Portland Cement has weak tensile resistive abilities, very porous in nature and is susceptible to moisture ingress under humid conditions and thermal stressed induced cracking which exposes the Reinforcing Bars within Reinforced Concrete vulnerable to the mercy of the weather. These cracks do not show any visual sign until they break the surface, exposing the structure to more accelerated deterioration(Aggelis et al. 2010). In this project, we take advantage of deep learning, utilizing a data-driven, stochastic structural damage detection method that convolutional neural networks (DCNN)(He et al. 2021). Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is designed to detect and extract structural damage features from the time-frequency images and distinguish different structural damage condition(Chen et al. 2021). Our SHM system focuses on Crack detection using images obtained from a camera mounted on a UAV. The UAV obtained numerous, varying angles of the independence Arc. (Malche, Tharewal, and Dhanaraj 2023)

The whole system can be broken down in to the following system components

- i. Sensor Network
- ii. Data Acquisition and Processing
- iii. Damage Detection
- iv. Damage Control

Figure 7-Damage Detection Summary

SYSTEM SELECTION CONSIDERATIONS

After an in-depth desk study and reconnaissance site visits to ascertain the real time functional conditions. We established the following based empirical and data recorded on site;

- We observed a vast temperature gradient averaging 25-degree Celsius owing to proximity to the Atlantic Ocean and High Day Time Temperature
- The Monument is not exposed to critical loadings and had an average daily Tourist Visitor throughput of 3500 individuals.
- Onsite Tidal Wave and Wind Data are still being collected as we are still writing this report but according to the Meteorological Agency’s Annual wind speed data recorded over 5 decades, there are not a lot of variation. In this era of Climate change, we cannot only rely on historical data but we need real time data also to make better situational judgements. The On-Site observed local data classified the site according to ASCE-7 as Wind Exposure Category D.

Figure 8-Aerial View Of the Independence Arch and the Atlantic Ocean

and saline conditions which often leads to rod corrosion, further leading to diminished rod sizes and eventually leading inadequate strength of Structural Elements.

The computer vision model and was trained on a large dataset obtained from the internet, which was annotated manually to ensure accuracy. The model was then tested on new data, and the results showed that it could accurately detect and identify structural damage on concrete structures with a **94% accuracy**. The system is much faster and more efficient than manual inspection, reducing the time and cost required for damage assessment. The proposed system has the potential to revolutionize the way we perform damage assessment on concrete structures. It can help to preserve and protect these valuable assets by enabling the early detection of damage and facilitating timely repairs(Malche, Tharewal, and Dhanaraj 2023).

After carefully considering and analyzing all the crucial and factors, such as cost, time line, criticality of damage we decided to perform the Crack detection structural damage assessment since the inherent conditions made our national Monument extremely susceptible to cracking and due to concrete porous probability, further cracks make the Reinforcing Bars extremely vulnerable to harsh humid

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE- DAMAGE DETECTION OF THE INDEPENDENCE ARK

Figure 9- Summary of Experiment Procedure

The following paragraphs further explains our experimental procedure.

THE SENSOR

The Sensor- A sensor is basically a device or an object which has the ability to convert a measurable physical quantity, such as pressure electrical voltage or impedance. An assembly of sensor measuring quantities give rise to what we usually team as sensor network. Sensor selection is very crucial to any Structural Health Monitoring System. The considerations at this stage are

- i. Most likely damage Analysis type
- ii. Local Availability of technology and requisite expertise
- iii. Budget
- iv. Wide Applicability

Figure 10-Unmanned Aerial Vehicle to Capture Images

Focusing on our case, we selected a camera mounted UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle). Mainly because cracks are a function of optical damage. Even though majority of cracks beyond a specific threshold value are not visible to the human eye, they can be detected with the help of technological advancements, they be detected. In recent times, UAV have been equipped with LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) technology to generate high data measurements to create topographical maps and accurate geophysical data. It has been really beneficial in disaster management when rescuers are ascertaining damage extent in planning for the next steps. (Structures n.d.)

DATA ACQUISITION AND SIGNAL PROCESSING

DATA ACQUISITION

This section primarily deals with the raw features obtained from our structure which we intend to characterize and detect Structural Damage. Dealing specifically with our situation, our data are the various images of the various sections of the Independence Ark. Due to the flexibility of the UAV-Technology as well as the influence of inherent conditions (daylight and nightlight.), we obtained varying angled, and varied coloration of the images.

SIGNAL PROCESSING

This section deals with all the activities we need to undertake in order for process our data and be able to detect damage; especially damage that isn't visible to the naked eye. Artificial neural networks (ANN) have been employed to classify to obtain surface damage information, such as the total amount of superficial cracking(Kabir 2010).

CNN-ARCHITECTURE

The convolutional Neural Network is modelled with the Python Programming Language version 3.12. We installed the Anaconda Python Navigator to enable us interact with the computer system. To better understand the role of the Anaconda Navigator, can be likened to a waiter who is serving various meals during a dinner banquet. Anaconda Navigator primary provides various programming environments for performing various task and computer tasks.

Figure 11-Anaconda Navigator Programming Environment

Our model can be built within the Jupyter Lab and the Jupyter Notebook. Between the Jupyter Lab and Jupyter Notebook, provides great flexibility to issue code instructions to be executed by the computer. We are inclined with to use Jupyter Lab because it easily provides great access to Anaconda Assistant, which is an AI, which provides support to user who usually encounter challenges while using the Programming Environment.

BUILDING THE NEURAL NETWORK

The Neural Network can be imagined as a multi-layered complex network of neurons who communicate with each other and perform specific tasks. Let us have a look at our various network layers

The Input Layer

This first layer of our Neural Network likened to the Gateway Entrance Point of Our Neural Network. Image data is actually derived from varying combinations of the Multidimensional Image Tensor usually with dimensionality of 3, where the dimensions are indicated in the following order; image number, Image Width and Image Height

Figure 12-Image Tensor Example

The Convolutional Layer

This is where the magic lives. This layer is where specific features our original data image is obtained and the process of convolutional filtering begins. key things to highlight here are Stride and Activation.

Stride is defined as the number of pixels that are used within an image's convolutional cycle.

Figure 13-Image Data Convolution

Figure 14- Max Pooling

The Pooling Layer

This layer acts as the data set squeeze extractor. It significantly reduces the size of our data and only

keeps the maximum pixel value. It aids the network perform efficiently by easing the cramming data flow while preventing overfitting

The Activation Function

Activation can be likened to the switch of the system. If the specific data feature meets a specific threshold requirement; then it permit it to move to the next layer of the network. There are 3 popular Activation Function types which are

The Sigmoid functions are S-Shaped graph functions which can mainly be categorized into 2 main functions

- The Logistic Function
- The Hyperbolic Tangent

The ReLU is also nicknamed the vanishing gradient situation. Its bounds are [0,1]. It mimics a system where when the output is a negative number, the system returns zero and returns 1 for positive values.

Figure 15 - Activation Function

Figure 16- Graphical Representation of Activation Functions

FLATTENING LAYER

This layer virtually compresses our data being processed through the System. It greatly improves the efficiency of our Neural Network.

IMPROVING NETWORK PERFORMANCE

This section describes the various task we performed to aid our system in working more efficiently. These are:

- **Data Augmentation**: This describes various image manipulation techniques such as cropping, rotating, flipping that helps the Neural network to better understand and detect structural damage
- **Normalizing**: Standard RGB images are 8 bits, with pixel values ranging from 0 to 255. To make our model work better we re-scale our image data to range within the boundary [0-1]. Mathematically it can be expressed as; $X = x/255$
- **Whitening/GreyScaling**: This is simply minimizing the error due to color deviation of RGB image data. Mathematically, it can be explained as setting the standard deviation of the data set as 1 and the mean of the data set as 0.

DAMAGE DETECTION –

TRAINING AND VALIDATION

Training- This stage is likened to teaching an infant how to identify colors or shapes. On the very first attempt, it is very difficult for the child to accurately identify images of colours, but upon further studying which in this case is training our convolutional neural network. Similar to the above-mentioned scenario, what is most critical is the our training dataset.

For the purposes of our study, training our Convolutional Neural Network primarily entails teaching it to classify images passing through the system as either a crack or an un-cracked image. This type of image classification technique is generally called Binary Classification. Our Network Assigns 0 when it detects a crack within an image frame and 1 when it does not detect a crack within the image.

The Dataset from which our CNN is taught to identify and detect cracks is always pivotal. Upon reading various research papers, Academic reviews and Academic Journals over the past 5 years, we discovered that the most reliable and easily accessible dataset we could utilize for training our CNN was the data obtained from Kaggle. Kaggle is a data modelling and data analysis platform, which was set up as a subsidiary of Google LLC in April 2010, to provide numerous strategies to best solve predictive modelling problems. Our dataset contained 20,000 varying images of cracked data and 20,000 varying images of cracked data. The reliability of the CNN's ability to accurately detect and predict structural cracks is largely dependent on the Dataset it trains with. Not necessarily on the quantity of the training dataset, but the rather the quality and diverse nature. Consider a scenario, teaching an infant colours with the same approach and no diverse strategy or technique adaptation might lead to the infant just memorizing colour names and making accurate predictions. In such situations, the training process has not led to learning. Training over varying conditions and larger datasets improves the convolutional network's ability to accurately predict and detect cracks.

SUMMARIZED PROCEDURE

Figure 17- CNN MODELLING PROCEDURE

IMPORTING LIBRARIES

The libraries are imported into the Virtual Environment's Notebook to perform specific task highlighted below. They are a collection of pre-written codes that are assigned to perform a specific task.

ASSIGN DATA PATH DIRECTORIES

```
In [15]: DATA_PATH = Path("TF/archive")
os.listdir(DATA_PATH)[:10]

Out[15]: ['CRACK', 'NO-CRACK']

In [16]: # IMAGE_FILES = glob.glob(f"{str(DATA_PATH)}/*/*.jpg")

In [57]: DATA = tf.keras.utils.image_dataset_from_directory(str(DATA_PATH))
DATA = DATA.map(lambda x,y: (x/255,y))
Found 40000 files belonging to 2 classes.
```

- The line Highlighted in Blue is the file Path Directory
- The line Highlighted in Yellow Normalizes the data

```

Jupyter Untitled Last Checkpoint: 10 hours ago (autosaved)
File Edit View Insert Cell Kernel Widgets Help
+ - < > Run C Code
In [58]: TF_ITERATOR = DATA.as_numpy_iterator()
In [59]: batch = TF_ITERATOR.next()
In [61]: # batch[0][1]
In [53]: label2id = {"crack": 0, "uncracked": 1}
id2label = {0: "crack", 1: "uncracked"}

# img = batch[0][20]
# label = batch[1][20]

# plt.figure(figsize=(10, 10))
# plt.imshow(img.astype(int))
# plt.title(f"Target: {id2label[label]}")
# plt.show()

In [62]: def visualize_cracks(batch):
rows = 4
cols = 8

fig, axes = plt.subplots(rows, cols, figsize=(12,12))
axes = axes.flatten()

for i in range(rows*cols):
img = batch[0][i]
l = batch[1][i]
label = id2label[l]
axes[i].imshow(img)
axes[i].set_title(f"{label}: {l}")
axes[i].axis(False)

plt.tight_layout()

visualize_cracks(batch)

```

This section converts the Tensorflow dataset in Numpy Array numbers, To Facilitate processing by the Neural Network

Code for Visualizing a 32 batch of classified images

A random Batch Element Display

TRAINING AND TESTING ALGORITHMS

```
In [64]: train_size = int(len(DATA)*.7)
        val_size = int(len(DATA)*.2)
        test_size = int(len(DATA)*.1)

        train = DATA.take(train_size)
        val = DATA.skip(train_size).take(val_size)
        test = DATA.skip(train_size+val_size).take(test_size)
```

THE CNN MODEL STRUCTURE

Model

```
In [65]: from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
        from tensorflow.keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Dense, Flatten, Dropout
```

```
In [68]: model = Sequential()

        model.add(Conv2D(16, (3,3), 1, activation='relu', input_shape=(256,256,3)))
        model.add(MaxPooling2D())

        model.add(Conv2D(32, (3,3), 1, activation='relu'))
        model.add(MaxPooling2D())

        model.add(Conv2D(16, (3,3), 1, activation='relu'))
        model.add(MaxPooling2D())

        model.add(Flatten())
        model.add(Dense(256, activation='relu'))
        model.add(Dense(1, activation='sigmoid'))

        model.compile('adam', loss=tf.losses.BinaryCrossentropy(), metrics=['accuracy'])

        model.summary()

Model: "sequential_1"
```

Model: "sequential_1"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 254, 254, 16)	448
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 127, 127, 16)	0
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 125, 125, 32)	4,640
max_pooling2d_4 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 62, 62, 32)	0
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(None, 60, 60, 16)	4,624
max_pooling2d_5 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 30, 30, 16)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 14400)	0
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 256)	3,686,656
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 1)	257

Total params: 3,696,625 (14.10 MB)

Trainable params: 3,696,625 (14.10 MB)

Non-trainable params: 0 (0.00 B)

Figure 18- CNN MODEL SUMMARY

MODEL METRICS

Figure 19-CNN Model Crack Prediction Accuracy

```

In [70]: fig = plt.figure()
         plt.plot(hist.history['loss'], color='teal', label='loss')
         plt.plot(hist.history['val_loss'], color='orange', label='val_loss')
         fig.suptitle('Loss', fontsize=20)
         plt.legend(loc="upper left")
         plt.show()
  
```


Figure 20- CNN LOSS FUNCTION PLOT

DAMAGE CONTROL

After our CNN, has done its job of detecting cracked structural surfaces, it times for us as Engineers to do what we like doing best; finding innovative, practical, economic and efficient solutions to our problems. With regards to concrete structures, there are 2 main damage control approaches. These are:

The following paragraphs further explains these concepts.

- Self-Healing- With this, control techniques are employed as soon the crack damage has occurred. Usually, provision for it is made during the design and construction phase, and is activated as soon damage occurs.
- Post-Damage Occurrence. This control mechanism entails, engineers suing various technology and techniques to detect damage and estimate its severity in order to make provision for it.
-

▪ *Figure 21- Summary of Crack Damage Control*

SELF-HEALING

It primarily outlines various mechanisms and required repair materials for concrete self-healing. Two self-healing techniques, namely microcapsule self-healing and microbial self-healing, have been developed. The combination of multiple self-healing techniques often yields excellent self-healing effect compared with the single technique. (Zhang et al. 2024).

Figure 22 - Self Healing Concrete

Microbially induced carbonate precipitation (MICP) provides an eco-friendly concrete repair alternative. MICP involves the ingress of calcium ions in to the concrete mix matrix at a specified time prior to the time casting. In some special cases, a hybrid approach is used where, a combined approach is utilized. For the Micro-bacteria application a bacterial solution (such as ureolytic bacterium *Sporosarcina Pasteurii*) is injected into crack and then the crack surface was adhered with a sponge containing the

saturated cementation solution (urea and calcium acetate) for continuous ion diffusion. White precipitations usually erupt within the cracks are confirmed to be calcium carbonate crystals existed in form of vaterite..(Lu et al. 2023)

POST DAMAGE REMEDY

Two main techniques highlighted earlier are;

Spot/line Application (Injection Method)- This technique is usually employed when the detected cracks are large enough to the extent that they are visible to the naked eye. The application methodology is highlighted below

- Substrate Preparation
- Insertion of T-plugs
- Preparation and Injection of repair mix
- Removal of plugs and Setting

Membrane Area Application- This technique is usually employed in either one of the following situations.

- Cracks detected are existent but inconspicuous to the naked eye
- Crack pattern is widespread within a specified area; similar alligator crack patterns
- Crack sizes detected are smaller than repair needle sizes; hence the injection method is not suitable for such applications.

EPOXY AS A REPAIR MATERIAL

Over the past decade epoxy resin was used to repair the fractured concrete, and has performed remarkably well. (Qing et al. 2023). Across the west African sub-region, it has become the repair material of choice for already existent structure. Aside Epoxy's ready availability, it is considered environmentally friendly and also had a wide colour applicability range. This does not raise eyebrows after repair works and keeps the general public a clear conscience while patronizing the edifice and promote Tourism as a major economic booster of the Ghanaian Economy. Hence it is considered the most suitable structural damage repair material.

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